

Volumetric Studies in Redox Reactions Part-I. Determination of Mercury(II) by Chloramine-T

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Manuscript received 11 February 1976, accepted 26 September 1977

Mercury (II) has been reduced to elemental state with formaldehyde solution in alkaline medium and determined with chloramine-T in a strong hydrochloric acid medium after pretreating with iodine monochloride. The end point is detected as in Andrews titration. The method gives accurate and reproducible results.

THE use of chloramine-T as an oxidising titrant was first proposed by Noll¹. Rupp² used chloramine-T for the determination of antimony (III) and later for the determination of tin(II). Komarowsky³ *et al* determined several compounds with chloramine-T. In a strong hydrochloric acid medium, in the presence of iodine monochloride, iodide, hydrazine, iron (II), arsenic(III), antimony(III), tin(II), mercury (I) and thiocyanate have been titrated with chloramine-T⁴. The present paper describes the use of chloramine-T as a titrant for estimation of mercury (II). It is based on the reduction of mercury (II) to the elemental state with formaldehyde solution in alkaline medium and subsequent determination of the precipitated mercury without separation, with chloramine-T in a strong hydrochloric acid medium, after pretreating with iodine monochloride. The end point is obtained as in the Andrew titration⁵ by the use of carbon tetrachloride.

All the chemicals used were analytical grade BDH Analar or Merck GR. Solution of mercury(II) was prepared by dissolving mercury(II) chloride in distilled water and its strength determined by iodine⁶. Iodine monochloride was prepared from potassium iodide and potassium iodate.

Procedure :

A suitable aliquot of mercury (II) solution was pipetted into a titration flask and 1 ml of formaldehyde solution (40%) followed by 10 ml of 4 N sodium hydroxide was added. The contents of the flask were allowed to stay for about two minutes to complete precipitation of mercury. The contents of the flask were then acidified with hydrochloric acid and to give an acid strength of about 5 N in the solution and 5 ml of iodine monochloride followed by 5 ml of carbon tetrachloride added. The reaction mixture was vigorously shaken to dissolve the precipitated mercury and the iodine liberated was titrated with a standard solution of chloramine-T. The end point was taken at the stage where the last trace of

violet colour disappeared from organic layer. The results are recorded in the table.

TABLE—1 ESTIMATION OF MERCURY (II) BY CHLORAMINE-T.

Sr. No.	Amount taken (mg.)	Amount Found (mg.)
1	40	39.9
2	60	60.1
3	80	79.9
4	100	99.7
5	120	120.3
6	160	159.9

Formaldehyde precipitates mercury(II) from its solution in alkaline medium :

The precipitated mercury is dissolved in iodine monochloride and the equivalent amount of iodine released (eq 2) is titrated with chloramine-T as in Andrews titration :

Excess of formaldehyde does not interfere in the determination. The method is accurate and utilizes only one standard solution. It is of practical value in the determination of sublimate in which mercury cannot be determined with thiocyanate by Volhard's method.

The interference of acetate, sulphate, phosphate, oxalate, bromide, nitrate, borate, arsenic (V), antimony (V), nickel (II), zinc (II), cobalt (II), lead (II), and cadmium (II) was investigated by adding 80 mg of each ion and it has been found that they do not interfere in the titration. However, manganese (II),

arsenic(III), antimony(III), mercury (I), silver (I) and copper (II) interfere in the determination.

Acknowledgement

The authors express their thanks to the authorities of Regional Engineering College, Kurukshetra for providing research facilities and to Prof. H.L. Bhatnagar for his keen interest and encouragement during the investigation.

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